

DESIGN & PHILOSOPHY.

FRIEDRICH NIETZSCHE'S THOUGHT AND THE TWENTIETH-CENTURY BUILDINGS DESIGN.

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ABSTRACT

This article analyzes Nietzsche's philosophical thinking impact on twentieth-century buildings history, namely its connection to Peter Behrens and Alessandro Mendini's methodological actions.

The authors identify the analogy between two projects: 'AEG Turbine Factory' (1907-1909) by Behrens and 'Groninger Museum' (1989-1994) by Mendini. This research focuses on the Nietzschean proposal, interpreting the history of man as an ever changing process.

We expect to contribute towards understanding European cities construction, challenging designers and architects to comprehend change as a synonym for the life cycle of the existing buildings (Venturi, 1966; Branzi, 1984; Latour, Yaneva, 2008). This translates into searching project solutions as pattern systems (Alexander, 1968) able to transform during the change that buildings are subject to.

We conclude arguing that each reality is a clear image of a system of thinking (Le Corbusier, 1922) and that design plays a key role in the today cities transformation and promotion.

Keywords: Design & Space, Systems of Patterns, Cities Construction, Design of Experience, Research Methodologies.

Introduction

This paper aims to demonstrate that the interpretation of philosophical thinking applied to the project should be built according to the reality the designer intends to analyze.

In the first section we relate Friedrich Nietzsche's thought to Peter Behrens' architecture project and to Alessandro Mendini's methodological action, to support the influence of the German philosopher on the twentieth century project culture.

In the second part we analyze two projects, one by Peter Behrens (1907-1908) and another by Alessandro Mendini (1989-1994). Both cases considered show that the proposed interpretation of the two designers reflects a mindset assuming a metamorphic and ambiguous relationship between individual and buildings, being existential, communicative, functional and emotional. We conclude the two proposals - Behrens' Turbinenhalle and Mendini's museum - reflect their day and age and as Bruno Latour and Albena Yaneva referred, "(...) a building is not a static object but a moving project, and that even once it has been built, it ages, it is transformed by its users, modified by all of what happens inside and outside, and that it will

pass or be renovated, adulterated and transformed beyond recognition” (Latour, Yaneva, 2008).

As if the surface were a cinematographer of images (Sartre, 1936) between nature and imagination, which applied to the project may constitute something between referent and appearance.

In the twenty-first century it involves relating culture to the unknown and risk to invention, in order to create something that is more than what is seen, assuring the individual is involved with the city as an experience of existence.

RATIONALE OF THE SUBJECT

In Peter Berhens' Germany from the beginning of the twentieth-century, intellectuals yearned for a proposal to disrupt Romantic vision of the world (*Weltanschauung*). Friedrich Nietzsche's thought, whose production ranges from balanced to alienated (Aschheim, 1994), will mainly be applauded after his death, both by German intellectuals and by the French generation from the 1960's. Nietzsche formulates an interpretation proposal for the world, noting the nihilistic situation reflected those days and consisted of the need of the individual to liberate from God's existence as a rationalization of man's will. This interpretation also becomes liberating from theological thought of that time, a possibility allowing the individual to find courage in himself and not in a divine reason, allowing power of will (*Wille zur Macht*) to be the general condition for practical reason. As Nietzsche claims about courage, "it also requires a preemptive force for reasons that today no one dares; courage to the forbidden; predestination to the labyrinth. (...) And the will to economize in the grand manner - to hold together his strength, his enthusiasm... Reference for self; love of self; absolute freedom of self..." (Nietzsche, 1895). Nietzsche's proposition, resulting from the reflection on late 19th century reality, is that courage is the true base for Being, or rather that courage is synonym to space time and the unplanned. As Nietzsche states "we are compelled to experience this illusion, totally caught up in it and constituted by it, as the truly non-existence, that is, as a continuing development in time, space and causality, in other words, as empirical reality. But if we momentarily look away from our own "reality," if we grasp our empirical existence and the world in general as an idea of the primordial oneness created

in every moment, then we must now consider our dream as the illusion of an illusion, as well as an even higher fulfilment of the original hunger for illusion." (Nietzsche, 1872). Nietzsche's statement confirms the human representation as an appearance of change it represents of itself. As if man was a symbol of himself with no restrictions for any individual. Causality is understood as a hypothesis, as a circumstance that according to the author must be taken into account in the interpretation of the reality in which the individual interacts. Hence the external factors while unplanned (such as culture and technological capabilities, to name a few), promote change and belong to the definition of courage according to Nietzsche, in the sense that courage manifests as an image of itself. But how is it possible to project the appearance of change? Or even how is it possible to project a Being that is endlessly changeable? This investigation concerns the interpretation of Nietzsche's thought regarding the design of buildings and not while interpretation of the human condition. Obviously the implementation of this proposal in the scope of housing experienced by the Nietzschean individual (which is by definition a watching individual) can be interpreted as a visual space that projects the appearance of becoming. There is change; hence there is appearance, Therefore appearance must be an endlessly modifiable entity. And this can only happen if courage is projected at all times and in different times. As defended by Nietzsche: "what started as appearance in the end nearly always becomes essence and effectively acts as its essence! What kind of a fool would believe that it is enough to point to this origin and this misty shroud of delusion in order to destroy the world that counts as 'real', so-called 'reality'! Only as creators can we destroy! – But let us also not forget that in long run it is enough to create new names and valuations and appearances of truth in order to create new 'things'. (Nietzsche, 1882). For this reason the appearance is achieved through representation. Firstly, the buildings are forms of visual space, of change and its relationship with representation is also a projection. It is the role of the watching designer to project a building endlessly changeable as something that is on the threshold between what the building was and what it will be, proposing solutions predisposed to change and for this reason, responses promoting the relationship

between what is the essence and what is the appearance of the building at each stage of the project. As explained by Gilles Deleuze: “that the present moment is not a moment of being or of present ‘in the strict sense’, that it is the passing moment, forces us to think of becoming, but to think of it precisely as what could not have started, and cannot finish becoming. What is the being of that which becomes, of that which neither starts nor finishes becoming? Returning is the being of what which becomes”. (Deleuze, 2006).

Therefore, regarding the project, it can be argued that Peter Behrens’s proposal is based on ‘Wille zur Macht’ by Friedrich Nietzsche, holding the quality of the final relationship established by the various forces and not just by the elementary articulating parts as is the case of autonomous thinking. The stronger the relationship, the better the final quality of the whole, hence, Nietzsche’s process demands stepping back to the origin, to classics, to cultural symbols, in order to award meaning to individual’s life. If forces are strong, the relationship is more intense and this will originate a final product that is more ambitious and powerful.

Another condition supporting the theory that Behrens methodological action was Nietzschean concerns the fact that Friedrich Nietzsche’s thought had been appropriated by the ‘Deutscher Werkbund’ association arising in the beginning of the twentieth-century. This association, directly controlled by politicians, industrials and artists including Peter Behrens, intended to reorganize the relationship between craftsmanship and industry. As noted by Steven. E. Aschheim, the ‘Deutscher Werkbund’ also included project professionals: “(...) various circles – especially of architects and craftsmen – sought to give practical expression to his inspirations through the creation of real and imagined Nietzschean ‘life styles’. The most famous and striking example was the work of Peter Behrens. Behrens designed his own Zarathustrian villa as a centerpiece of the experimental Darmstadt artists’ colony. The house was adorned with symbols such as the eagle, Zarathustra’s diamond, and the Edelstein that radiated the virtues of a world which is not yet here.” (Aschheim, 1994).

This project by Peter Behrens is analyzed by Manfredo Tafuri and Francesco Dal Co (1976) and compared to a surreal cave, alluding to Plato’s cave,

being built in the hall of the German Pavilion for the Turin Exhibition of 1902, to represent the new spirit of German society and a new projectual order. This methodology started by Peter Behrens extends to other designers from that time such as Walter Gropius or Le Corbusier, among others.

According to Le Corbusier, for instance, the issue of order in architecture does not exist for some designers in his time, because the projectual reference was architecture and not thought. In particular, when Le Corbusier (1922) questions the constructive order based on History of Architecture, advocating a methodological action, he expresses the need for the built product to reflect the rationality of the historical moment, “An era creates its own architecture, which is the clear image of a system of thought).” (Le Corbusier, 2008). This discussion will characterize the entire twentieth century extending to our days as a consistent theme in its timeliness, being a core project argument for designers.

However, this study intends to examine the influence of Nietzsche's thought in the design of the surface of buildings from the twentieth-century and not to analyze designers’ operating mode. That was why we searched for a designer operating in a different reality and different age, expressing the influence of Nietzsche's thought, in order to substantiate architectural building as a consequence of a given system of thought reflecting a particular historical period, specifically a moment in the end of the twentieth-century.

Moving back to the 1960’s, the classic projectual ‘method’ supported by science and product-oriented revealed its weakness by ignoring external factors inherent to the process and to the impact on the user of the end product. Those external factors ironically emerged in response to massification and to the new pop culture characterizing the Western context. In Italy, the Italian radical project movements like UFO, Superarchitettura or Archizoom Associati presented new solutions that Paolo Deganello advocates were an alternative to the exact model of ‘good design’ from the ‘Hochschule für Gestaltung’ in Ulm. These were projectual responses with no pretension of public education as promised by the ‘Hochschule für Gestaltung’ in Ulm, but rather “to bring its

deconsecrated way of inhabiting onto architecture.” (Deganello, 2009)¹.

Would it then present an argument in favor of breaking with the architecture from a recent past or rather intended to redefine the issue of industrial society project, inherited from the Modern Movement? Would it be a proposal for a society characterized by transience and new consumption rhythms typical in a younger population?

Concerning the inadequacy of architecture to apply a standard ‘method’, with the same rule for every plan, in architecture, urban planning or design, an inclusive process emerges, driven by design, gathering all positive and negative factors in order to respond by means of conjecture and admitting doubt, instead of supplying a single unchanging response.

These contradictions and sudden changes demanded a project Andrea Branzi (1999) defines as ‘weak and diffuse’, a project conceived to fit a context and able to simultaneously signify everything and its opposite. A project exercise that in order to interpret the city intersects with other disciplines, resulting from the impact of urban flows (flow of people, goods and information) in the contemporary city, more important than the material existence of buildings specially concerning information and communication: “The medium is the message. Any understanding of social and cultural change is impossible without knowledge of the way media work as environments.” (McLuhan; Fiore, 2008). Projectual activity, thus, emerged as militant and critical expression for eventual crisis situations.

In 1972, in ‘Learning from Las Vegas’ Robert Venturi, Denise Scott-Brown and Steven Izenour criticize the symbolic context of the International Style and the architects who reject the use of symbolism. “Symbols dominate space. Architecture is not enough. And because space relationships are established with symbols, more than with forms, the architecture of this landscape becomes a symbol in space more than a form in space.” (Venturi, Scott-Brown & Izenour, 2008)². The three authors agree upon the existence of

advertising as message and of the surface of buildings as its carrier.

In this sense, in ‘Complexity and Contradiction in Architecture’ Robert Venturi (1966) argues in the form of a manifest that architecture must be complex, contradictory, ambiguous, tense and inclusive, rejecting the International Style. Yet this does not mean Venturi rejects the existing contradictions in the Modern Movement, as for instance with Alvar Aalto or Le Corbusier. Actually, for Robert Venturi, the designer is free to choose and combine modern grammar with historical elements: ornamentation and minimalism, mass or limited series, the finest materials and kitsch. Robert Venturi’s proposal regarding the complexity and contradiction in the consumer society is shared by Alessandro Mendini (1979) in his essay ‘Per un’Architettura Banale’, advocating the concept of ‘banal design’ as a critical projectual proposal, “banal design, plainly quotidian, amoral and cynically self-acquainted.”³ For Alessandro Mendini this was a sarcastic, infringing, fracturing and anti-normative proposal, a promise of canvassing choices from the public instead of condemning them, integrating such choices in the project for being significant in the context. This highlighted the importance of the project as a means to communicate a symbolic message close to the ordinary quotidian, hence a project appropriating kitsch.

Later, in 1984, Alessandro Mendini publishes the ‘Manifesto di Alchimia’ in the magazine ‘Domus’, describing a new profile for the designer. A designer of the ordinary and bourgeois project, in a metissage and consume society. As advocated by Mendini, “we the bourgeois can yet only consciously design the progressive death of the bourgeois project.”⁴ Mendini refers to the project as a production of life, a clear allusion to Friedrich Nietzsche’s nihilism.

For Mendini, “this deliberately nihilistic approach, self wounding and cynical, allowed us to identify ourselves with the total blackout, to identify ourselves with the situation in which designers are unable to provide any answers.” (Mendini cit in Remakers, 1998).

¹ Translated from the Portuguese original. “trazer a sua maneira desconsagrada de habitar para dentro da arquitectura.” (Deganello, 2009: 183).

² Translated from the Spanish original. “El símbolo domina el espacio. La arquitectura no basta. Y como las relaciones espaciales se establecen más con los símbolos que con las formas, la arquitectura de este paisaje se convierte en símbolo en el espacio más que en forma en el espacio.” (Venturi, Scott-Brown & Izenour, 2008: 35).

³ Translated from the Italian original: in <http://www.ateliermendini.it>. (Accessed in 01/2011). “una progettazione banale, piattamente quotidiana, amorale e cinicamente nota a se stessa.”

⁴ Translated from the Italian original: in <http://www.ateliermendini.it>. (Accessed in 01/2011). “noi borghesi possiamo invece e solo progettare con coscienza la morte progressiva del progetto borghese.”

As 'interpreted' by Alessandro Mendini and his followers, there is an influence from Nietzsche's thought, namely regarding the relationship established among the quality of the forces of the cultural elements selected for the project. It is a composition of cultural symbols from the new pop culture massively disseminated for a massified user with massified comprehension and enjoyment.

Andrea Branzi highlights the presence of Nietzsche's thought in *Alchimia* by Alessandro Mendini when stating that "Mendini and Portoghesi represented the two extremes of that theoretical perspective, one being nihilistic and the other restorer."⁵ Therefore, the choice of symbols targets a message that is quick and accessible for the user to identify with the aesthetic experience and at first with the referent. A project is a 're-project'. As defended by Alessandro Mendini, "to reset means to make a fresh start, means erasing everything, to change everything, to reinvent from the beginning the relationship between the parties, to rebuild the whole system of terms in question, to create a clear boundary between a before and an after in which the after is totally different from before."⁶

In design, *Alchimia* and *Memphis* groups are those that best interpret this thought. However, the project group that applies the nihilistic proposal is *Alchimia*, founded in 1976 by Alessandro Mendini and based on the proposal of 'banal design' referring to design classics that seem to rise from a long hibernation as if being granted an eternal recurrence.

Alessandro Mendini explains in Silvia Paoli's text that "in the early eighties, some associated these forms with Nietzsche and 'negative thinking' (...)"⁷. For Alessandro Mendini, the end of a cycle was an opportunity to question the project. Design classics were allowed a new 'interpretation' in line with the new reality, as if the designers caused the death of the referent and at the same time awarded it new aspects in continuous cycle. This proposal kept the values of

the individual, following his evolution prone to hybridization, subsequently had a tangled vitality, illusion of new life.

On the subject of this projectual action Andrea Branzi states that "the amused use of 'uneducated' codes callously approaches the certainty that the object's surface is the unwavering limit of the project hence the only possible field of action."⁸

These projects had two guidelines corresponding to two types of 're-design': the redesign of famous projects as the chairs by Gerrit Rietveld, Joe Colombo, Charles Rennie Mackintosh or Marcel Breuer and the redesign of common objects such as the Proust armchair. As advocated by Andrea Branzi, "redesign is born as an attempt to demonstrate that nowadays, at least for the next ten years, we can only redesign."⁹

For Mary Douglas and Baron Isherwood (1979), it regarded the interpretation of the consume relations (the mirror of reality that is yet the current reality) as connections between objects and users. The objects turned into interpreters, providing the communication with the user, also fostering the relations of individuals with other individuals. As if the objects, extending their secondary role (Eco, 1971), were also suitable for the act of thinking, transforming into mediators of an experiential, interpretive, and continuous action with the users.

In its application to design it means that this symbolic process allows objects to be interpreted as conveyors of memories, by complex and changing individuals living in a contradictory and metamorphic reality.

⁵ Translated from the French original. "Mendini e Portoghesi rappresentavano i due punti estremi di questa linea teorica, l'un nihilista, l'altro restauratore." (Branzi, 1985: 127).

⁶ Translated from the Italian original: in <http://www.ateliermendini.it>. (Accessed in 01/2011). "rifondare significa fare 'tabula rasa', significa vuotare tutto, cambiare tutto, reinventare completamente il rapporto fra le parti, ricostituire tutto il sistema dei termini in questione, creare un confine preciso fra un prima e un dopo, dove il dopo sia tutto differente dal prima."

⁷ in http://www.tingo.it/img/fiori_di_luce_catalogo.pdf. (Accessed in 01/2011).

⁸ Translated from the French original. "l'utilisation amusée des codes 'incultes' côtoie froidement la certitude que la surface de l'objet est la limite incontournable du projet donc le seul champ d'action possible." (Branzi, 1985: 123).

⁹ Translated from the French original. "le re-design naît comme une tentative de démontrer qu'aujourd'hui, pour les dix ans à venir au moins, on ne peut plus que redessiner." (Branzi, 1985: 127).

Figure 1. Left to right: AEG Turbine Factory in Berlin-Moabit (1907-1909). Advertising medium for AEG lamps (1907). GB1 Fan (1908)

APPLICATION: PETER BEHRENS AND ALESSANDRO MENDINI

THE AEG TURBINE FACTORY (1907-1909) BY PETER BEHRENS

For Manfredo Tafuri and Francesco Dal Co, “the peak of this ideological framework is reached by Behrens in 1907, when P. Jordan suggests replacing Alfred Messel (1853-1909) - author of the Wertheim Department Store in Berlin (1904) in which neo-Gothic outlines a commercial typology with high urban value – as AEG consultant, the German electrical monopoly headed by Emil and Walter Rathenau.” (Tafuri; Dal Co, 1992)¹⁰.

With this in mind, Peter Behrens responds to the AEG brief repositioning for a highly competitive market of electrical products, blending art and technology. For Peter Behrens “technique cannot keep on being understood as a purpose in itself, but acquiring meaning and value when recognized as the most appropriate mean of culture.” (Behrens cit in Maldonado, 1999)¹¹. The forces of the parts should relate to form a stronger force hence the reference should be in historical past. Peter Behrens designs industrial objects, advertising material or even factory buildings interpreted as forces of parts of a whole that is AEG. The relationship between parts depends on

the force referenced in Greek culture, because the stronger the parts, the stronger the whole, meaning AEG company would be synonym to quality.

As mentioned by Manfredo Tafuri and Francesco Dal Co (1976), Peter Behrens interprets Friedrich Nietzsche’s thought through the project to the extent that for Peter Behrens, to ‘be strong’ meant referencing the project in a distant historical culture such as the Greek’s in Nietzsche’s proposal. Being heir to the Classical Greek culture Peter Behrens knew that a product referenced to this culture might bind the user to identification, meaning a predisposition to perform aesthetic experiences and also knowledge experiences.

As if Peter Behrens proposed a system of forces to justify the quality of the final product, a product system as global project.

Manfredo Tafuri and Francesco Dal Co also consider that “the factory, as urban object, is called to reflect - as the crystal from the inaugural show in Darmstadt - the very potential for urban planning. The whole urban structure must be mirrored in the example of this new social time, and the supreme synthesis expressed by the emblematic constructivism from the AEG building - work and art reunited - should be projected onto the typologies conveyed by the big city.” (Tafuri; Dal Co, 1992).¹²

¹⁰ Translated from the Italian original. “il culmine di tale linea ideologica è toccato da Behrens nel 1907, quando P. Jordan gli propone di sostituire Alfred Messel (1853-1909) - l'autore dei magazzini Wertheim a Berlino (1904), in cui il neogotico definisce una tipologia commerciale di alto valore urbano - come consulente dell'AEG, il monopolio elettrico tedesco diretto da Emil e Walter Rathenau.” (Tafuri; Dal Co, 1992: 81).

¹¹ Translated from the Portuguese original. “a técnica não pode continuar a ser entendida por mais tempo como finalidade em si própria, mas adquire valor e significado quando é reconhecida como o meio mais adequado de uma cultura.” (Behrens cit in Maldonado, 1999).

¹² Translated from the Italian original. “la fabbrica, in quanto oggetto urbano, é chiamata a riflettere - come il cristallo dello spettacolo inaugurale di Darmstadt - il proprio potenziale ordinatore sulla città. L'intera struttura urbana dovrà plasmarsi sull'esempio di questo nuovo <tempio sociale>, e la suprema sintesi espressa dal costruttivismo emblematico degli edifici dell' AEG - lavoro e arte riuniti - deve proiettarsi sulle tipologie portanti della grande città.” (Tafuri; Dal Co, 1992: 82).

Figure 2. Left to right: Groninger Museum, Holland, 1989-1994, by Atelier Mendini, in collaboration with artists and architects invited by the Alchimia group: Michele de Lucchi, Gerd Koster, Feruccio Laviani, Phillippe Starck, Frank Stella, Coop Himmelb(l)au, among others.

THE GRONINGER MUSEUM (1989-1994) BY ALESSANDRO MENDINI

One of the projects developed by Alessandro Mendini in Alchimia displaying the influence of Nietzsche's thought in the objects' surface is the Groninger Museum in Holland, started in 1989 and completed in 1994. It is a system of parts bringing together different forces, materialized in the choice of different international designers.

Mendini refuses to present a single project by a single author, preferring to choose different interventions by different designers such as Philip Starck, Michele de Lucchi, Frank Stella, the Coop Himmelb(l)au studio, among others. Hence, the whole (the museum), would be the result of the relationship of the quality of different forces (projects by different designers with different artistic backgrounds), assuring the meeting of the forces of the parts to result in a stronger force. According to Mendini, the individual needs a personality instead of functional design anonymity. "Every person is different, so why shouldn't an object be also different?"¹³

This hypothesis regards the object's beauty instead of its practical function insofar it is thought and made for the individual, not for the object.

Mendini's logical solution was then to present 4 different project proposals, connected by corridors, inviting designers to draw individual components. It was a careful analysis, interpretation and reconfiguration of historical backgrounds onto one consistent whole. As referred by Gianluca Marziani, it was "a place where space becomes dream, freedom

of mind, a journey beyond the limits of the known form." (Marziani, 2001: 115)¹⁴.

As advocated by Alessandro Mendini (1969) the instant for projectual thinking can be understood as an indirect formalization projectual behaviour. This meant the main problem in the project is the idea of making something reproducible, so that in a second stage it would become form. To consider the constructive order of the building surface as a pattern-system meant considering the body-surface as open and infinite prefabrication elements. In methodological terms it was a reference to the logic of numerical patterns by Alexander (1968) whereas surface of the city.

RESULTS

This article identifies analogies in the aesthetic understanding of two projects, from the beginning and the end of the twentieth-century, holding as reference Friedrich Nietzsche's thought, particularly concerning the history of a given time to be similar to future history but told differently.

Yet, building issues can no longer be exclusively regarded as architectural issues. The enigma of standard construction designed as a purpose in itself cannot operate this change on its own, since it is tied to its disciplinary and historical past and lacks distancing to be able to interpret change. The designer who knows the analogic moments in the history of architecture holds pre-knowledge about it, with no pre-judgments, since history is there to guide

¹³ <http://www.groningermuseum.nl/en/alessandro-mendini> (Accessed in Jan 2012).

¹⁴ Translated from the Italian original. "un luogo dove lo spazio diventa sogno, liberta mentale, viaggio oltre i limiti della forma conosciuta." (Marziani, 2001: 115).

him, offering references such as cultural signs, important elements to define the future. History is there to guide, not to restrain.

The designer thus assumes a great role with great responsibility in the transformation of the existing cities. Mingling with other professionals with different knowledge he makes the choice to think the building problem as a system of autonomous parts related to each other. If architectural building is significant for the way reality is thought, to reflect upon this issue nowadays means thinking about architectural design. It involves proposing ephemeral manifestations for the surface of buildings, reflecting the contemporary individual. For this reason it is essential for designers to understand the building life cycle, proposing project solutions as systems of objects able to transform within the building change within reality. Design's logistic ability to project systems of objects instead of compact and absolute bodies becomes an asset to solve the enigma of building. This rationale points to the building surface project as empty space to be managed by a pattern system, considerations indicating design as discipline able to raise awareness and responsibility of users, unveiling a society demanding unceasing transformation.

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